

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Perspectives of travelers on fundamental marketing techniques in Pondicherry Tourism

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Abstract

The Pondicherry tourism provides interest in cultural tourism, spiritualism, 'wellness' holidays, eco-tourism and rural tourism would tend to favour Pondicherry Tourists. It's provided the state can avail of the opportunities offered to maximize its natural advantages in these areas but it is observed that regional linkages, connectivity, accommodation. This study examined Perspectives of Travelers on Fundamental Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism.

Keywords: Tourism; Marketing Techniques; Pondicherry

1. Introduction

Tourism as a human activity has broadened and shared knowledge through travel and wandering, bringing civilizations closer than ever before. To make the tourism industry productive and its economic activities more productive, its basic law and organisational structure must be reformed to support services such as sea, air, and land transportation. Stability, safety, and security are the most significant and critical components necessary for any nation's tourism industry. Without them, economic activity becomes immobile owing to its great sensitivity to tourists' emotions of uneasiness in an unstable and secure country. According to Walker (2004), tourism is a dynamic, changing, consumer-driven force and one of the world's major businesses if all of its components are grouped together: travel accommodations, food service, and leisure. Tourism is expected to grow quickly in the next few years, which will bring both opportunities and problems for the public and private sectors to take advantage of.

2. Review of Related Literature

The study by **Gunarekha, B.S., et al. (2017)** is an early effort to compare the satisfaction of local and international visitors with tourism marketing tactics. The four marketing methods examined in this research were a product, pricing, location, and promotion. The research investigated whether or not there are substantial differences in product strategy between local and international visitors. It was determined that domestic visitors were happier with the product strategy of the Hampi tourism business compared to international tourists. In addition, domestic and international visitors were equally satisfied with the pricing, location, and marketing techniques of the Hampi tourism business.

In the research, **Aggarwal S. (2016)** emphasised the elements determining visitors' happiness with religious visits. This research was done in Brij Keshtara, where it was determined that tourist attractiveness is essential for the sustainable growth of certain locations, consequently leading to the sustainable development of locations. The research attempted to achieve its goal by using criteria important for total satisfaction in Brij Keshtara. The research indicated that five factors aesthetic appeal, accessibility, supporting infrastructure, food and service, health, and guide have a substantial link with tourist satisfaction. They are aesthetic appeal, accessibility, supporting infrastructure, food and service, and

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health. In other words, the research may assist planners and marketers in the development of plans to monitor and promote tourism in Brij Keshtar.

As India is renowned for its fairs and festivals, **Prasad and Bhatia (2014)** concluded their research on visitor satisfaction at the famous Pushkar fair. After the conclusion of the fair, a structured questionnaire was utilised to solicit answers from visitors to fulfil the research requirements. In the research, a total of 17 elements were maintained under five factors: food, lodging, security factor, sightseeing, communication, and public service, with food and lodging having the greatest influence, followed by security, communication, sightseeing, and public service. Finally, a link between visitor contentment was discovered.

3. Research Design and Sample

This study is concerned with specific prediction, with the narration of facts and opinions of individual tourists. The study also focuses on Tourists' opinions of Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism. In this scenario, the study checks the importance and relevance of present conditions described by descriptive research. This study aims to describe the current scenario of Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism and for that, this method is appropriate. So, the study chooses the 100 samples from the method of Simple Random sampling method, based on the simple probability technique, in which the researcher decides on samples from a larger population using an approach based on probability theory.

3.1. Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Model Fit Summary

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	S.E of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
Marketing Techniques	0.952	0.906	0.899	0.23497	2.197

3.1.1. Dependent Variable: Marketing Techniques

Model reveals that R- (Multiple Correlation Coefficients) value is 0.952. It is measuring the degree of relationship between the Marketing Techniques and the predicted values like, Hotels for foods are comfortable and hygienic (MT-1), The rooms provide basic amenities for tourists (MT-2), Availability of different rates to suit our need (MT-3), Travel packages are arranged according to the needs of the individuals (MT-4), No inconvenience when traveling in vehicles (MT-5), The basic tourism structure attracts me to Pondicherry (MT-6), and Details about destinations are provided as billboards at tourist sites (MT-7). R-Square (Coefficient of Determination) value is 0.906. It is more than about 90% of the variation of Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism. Adjusted R- squared value is 0.899. It adjusts the statistic based on the number of independent variables in the model. That is the desired property of goodness-of- fit statistic.

Furthermore, Durbin-Watson (DW) value exists $0 \rightarrow 4$ is good correction, ($0 \rightarrow 2$ is positive auto correction, $2 \rightarrow 4$ negative auto correction) here statistics shows 2.197, it is indicating positive auto correction, (i.e.) good correction.

Table 2 ANOVA

Marketing Techniques	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	48.881	7	6.983	126.482	0.000
Residual	5.079	92	.055		
Total	53.960	99			

3.1.2. Dependent Variable: Marketing Techniques

The *F*-ratio in the ANOVA table interprets the overall regression model, which is a normal fit for the data. The result of $F(7, 92) = 126.48$ and 'p' value 0.000 is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), the regression model is a good fit for the data; therefore, this model is a linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 3 Relationship between a linear combination of Perspectives of Travelers on Fundamental Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism

Marketing Techniques	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig. P-Value	95% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance (>0.2)	VIF (<5)
(Constant)	-0.29	0.148		-2.02	0.046	-0.59	-0.01		
MT -1	0.172	0.037	0.199	4.601	0.000	0.097	0.246	0.546	1.831
MT -2	0.188	0.041	0.211	4.547	0.000	0.106	0.270	0.475	2.105
MT -3	0.111	0.044	0.120	2.539	0.013	0.024	0.197	0.457	2.190
MT -4	0.113	0.044	0.134	2.554	0.012	0.025	0.202	0.373	2.679
MT -5	0.168	0.043	0.197	3.936	0.000	0.083	0.252	0.407	2.459
MT -6	0.117	0.032	0.148	3.712	0.000	0.054	0.180	0.647	1.545
MT -7	0.210	0.031	0.273	6.837	0.000	0.149	0.271	0.640	1.562

3.1.3. Dependent Variable: Marketing Techniques

The above table shows the independent variables of the Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism variables are highly significant; the p-values are less than 0.01. It can be seen that the values of VIF of all the predictor constructs are less than 5. The tolerance values the constructs are also more than 0.2. The VIF and Tolerance values are well within the stipulated limits as suggested in the extant literature. Hence, it can be inferred that there is no substantial level of multi collinearity among independent variable, which indicates that multi collinearity is not a problem in this model.

95% Confidence Interval for B's Lower Bound and Upper Bound, both values are positive or both values are negative; it is influence on Lower Bound and Upper Bound, here all variables Lower Bound and Upper Bound both values are positive, so it is significantly influence on Lower Bound and Upper Bound.

The above table derives the equation of Marketing Techniques dependent variables like

$$\text{Marketing Techniques} = -0.29 (\beta_0) + \beta_1(0.172) + \beta_2(0.188) + \beta_3(0.111) + \beta_4(0.113) + \beta_5(0.168) + \beta_6(0.117) + \beta_7(0.210)$$

4. Findings

The significant variables are comparing with Standardized Coefficients β -values; the resulted that the first influenced Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism is Details about destinations are provided as billboards at tourist sites (MT-7), the β -value is 0.273. The second influenced variable is the rooms provide basic amenities for tourists (MT-2), the β -value is 0.211. The third influenced variable is Hotels for foods are comfortable and hygienic (MT-1), the β -value is 0.199.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

The study concludes most influenced variables of Marketing Techniques in Pondicherry Tourism is 'Details about destinations are provided as billboards at tourist sites' and rooms provide basic amenities for tourists , furthermore Hotels for foods are comfortable and hygienic. The Pondicherry Tourism to improve the availability of different rates to suit for Tourist need and Travel packages are arranged according to the needs of the individuals.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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